

Synergic Effects in the Solvent Extraction of Ni (II) by Salicylaldehyde*

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The complex $\text{Ni}(\text{Sal})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is sparingly soluble in nonpolar solvents. However, it goes in solution in presence of pyridine and can also be extracted into these organic solvents. The extractability of this complex adduct into benzene is attributed to the replacement of water molecules by pyridine giving rise to synergic effects. The power dependencies of $[\text{HSal}]$, (Py) and $[\text{H}^+]$ have been determined. From the data obtained the extracted species appear to be $\text{Ni}(\text{Sal})_2\text{Py}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The behaviour of bivalent nickel is at times quite different from that of its analogues in the first transition series. Thus acetylacetone extracts copper (II) quantitatively, whereas the extraction of nickel (II) proceeds only to less than twenty per cent and that too very slowly¹. Absence of extraction or extraction with difficulty of nickel has been observed in the case of the chelates of dibenzoyl methane, TTA (thenoyl-trifluoro-acetylacetone), oxine, cupferron, etc.². However, an interesting observation is that cupferron can extract nickel into benzene in presence of iso-amyl alcohol. Other observations of interest are also those of Irving and Al-Niami³ who observed synergic effects in the extraction of nickel as the di-acetyl-bis-benzoylhydrazone in presence of donor molecules such as 4-methylpyridine.

It is known⁴ that the bis-salicylaldehyde chelate of nickel crystallizes with two molecules of water. The structure of this complex has been found to be octahedral⁵ with trans configuration. Such a complex should be very unfavourable for solvent extraction due to its low solubility in organic solvents like benzene. However, by replacement of the water with hydrophobic donor molecules it should be possible to solvent extract the complex and synergic effects should be observed. With this in view, studies on this chelate have been carried out and the results are reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by a procedure slightly different from the one given in literature⁴. A known amount of nickel chloride hexahydrate was dissolved in alcohol-water-mixture (1:1 by volume). A solution containing the theoretical amount of salicylaldehyde was also prepared in 1:1 alcohol-water mixture and the two solutions were mixed.

*Presented at the Indian Chemical Society Annual Convention, 1966 at Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidya Nagar, Anand.

1. J. Stary and E. Hlady, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1963, **28**, 227.
2. "The solvent extraction of metal chelates" by J. Stary, pergamon Press, 1964.
3. H.M.N.H. Irving and Al. Niami, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2231.
4. G. N. Tyson Jr. and S. C. Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 1228.

A small amount of dilute ammonia was added to adjust to the required pH when a pale green and thick precipitate settled at the bottom. It was quickly filtered and washed well. Care was taken to see that ammonia was never in excess to avoid any chance of salicylaldehyde formation. The precipitate was repeatedly washed with water, alcohol and ether and then dried over concentrated sulphuric acid. The complex was analysed for its nickel content gravimetrically as nickel dimethylglyoximate after destroying the organic matter by wet oxidation. Ni: Found, 17.24%; Required 17.41%.

Preliminary studies showed that the complex was insoluble in solvents like benzene and chloroform, but dissolved readily in presence of pyridine to give a greenish solution. It also readily dissolved in pure pyridine. The following procedure was used to prepare the pyridine 'adduct'. 5 g of the aquo complex was dissolved in excess pyridine and the clear dark solution was evaporated on a water bath. All pyridine evaporated off leaving a yellowish green amorphous powder, darker in colour than the dihydrate. It was kept in vacuum over con. H_2SO_4 to remove the excess pyridine. The purity of the complex was checked by analysing for nickel. Exp. 12.61% Ni; Calc. 12.78% Ni corresponding to $Ni(C_7H_5O_2)_2 \cdot 2Py$.

Solubilities of the above complexes in benzene were determined at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ after keeping stirred for 4 hr. The following values were obtained:

$Ni(C_7H_5O_2)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Negligible solubility
$Ni(C_7H_5O_2)_2 \cdot 2Py$	0.07M

Based on these results, solvent extraction experiments were carried out in presence and absence of pyridine according to the following procedure. 10 ml of $10^{-3}M$ nickel chloride in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer mixture (0.1M) was taken with 0.1M solution of salicylaldehyde in benzene, with or without pyridine, in a 50 ml stoppered test tube. The tube was shaken vigorously for 30 mts. in a shaking machine. The layers were carefully separated and removed into two 100 ml beakers. The solutions were evaporated to dryness and the organic matter destroyed. Nickel was determined absorptiometrically by the dimethylglyoxime method⁶.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1(a) and 1(b) and Fig. 2 show the extraction of nickel by salicylaldehyde with and without the addition of pyridine. The effect of pyridine on the extraction efficiency is obvious. There is approximately a ten-fold increase in the extraction (Fig. 1). The two extraction processes may be represented by the equations below:

5. E. O. Lingafelter et al., *Acta Cryst.*, 1957 **10**, 785.

6. "Colorimetric Analysis", E. B. Sandell, p. 671.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Equation (2) is written on the indirect evidence that the above complex has been formed and is more soluble in benzene. However, the replacement of water by pyridine may be only partial when the actual extraction is carried out (as explained later), giving rise to synergic effects in the extraction systems. It is reasonable to assume that the resistance of $Ni(Sal)_2(H_2O)_2$ to dissolve in solvents like benzene (preventing the extraction of nickel as the salicylate complex in such solvents) is due to the presence of the two bonded water molecules. Replacement of the two water molecules by pyridine makes the complex hydrophobic and extractable into non-donor solvents thus:

Species involved in the extraction equilibrium:

If we represent the extracted complex as $[Ni(Sal)_x(Py)_p]$, then we can get

$$D = \frac{[Ni(Sal)_x(Py)_p]_{org}}{\sum_o^N NiAc_n} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where D = distribution coefficient, Ac = acetate ion.

The species $[Ni(Sal)_2(H_2O)_2]_{org}$ and $\sum_e^{N/2} Ni(Sal)_n$ are in negligible amounts. Introducing a partition coefficient p and a stoichiometric stability constant β for the pyridine complex, a partition coefficient p_{py} for pyridine and β_1 as the stoichiometric stability

constants for the acetate complexes, we get

$$D = \frac{K' (\text{HSal})^x_{\text{org}} (\text{Py})^p_{\text{org}}}{\sum_{j=0}^N \beta_j (\text{Ac})}$$

where $K' = [p \beta K^x_{\text{HSal}} P_{\text{py}} P^x_{\text{HSal}}]$, K_{HSal} and P_{HSal} being respectively the dissociation constant and partition coefficient of (HSal). Taking decadic logarithms of both sides and partially differentiating with respect to one variable, e.g., $(\text{Py})_{\text{org}}$, and keeping the other two constant, i.e., (H^+) and $(\text{HSal})_{\text{org}}$, one can get the numbers x and p . The results as obtained from the figures 3, 4 and 5 are summarised as follows:

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

- (a) Dependence of $\log D$ on $\log (Py)_{org}$.. Unit power
 (b) ,, on $\log (HSal)_{org}$.. Unit power
 (c) ,, on pH .. Two power

An alternate method of determining the composition of the extracted species is by the method of continuous variations with equimolar solutions. The application of this method for a system involving the extraction of a metal chelate has been described by Irving and Pierce⁷. The present one being a mixed complex, the necessary mathematical treatment is given below. The extraction constant K is given by

$$K = \frac{[Ni(Sal)_x(Py)_p]_{org} [H]^x}{[Ni] [HSal]_{org}^x [Py]_{org}^p} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } (\Sigma Ni) &= [Ni] + \sum_0^N Ni Ac_n \\ &= [Ni] \left\{ \sum_0^N \beta_j [Ac]^j \right\} \quad \dots (7) \end{aligned}$$

However, the term within the double bracket is a constant at constant pH and acetate concentration. Therefore, $[Ni]$ is proportional to (ΣNi) . Thus, one can write that

$$D = \frac{[Ni(Sal)_x(Py)_p]_{org}}{[Ni]} \quad \dots (8)$$

After suitable rearrangement one can get

$$D = \text{cont. } [HSal]_{org}^x [Py]_{org}^p \quad \dots (9)$$

Under condition of continuous variation of equimolar solutions, if $[HSal]_{org} = [X]$, $[Py]_{org} = 1 - [X]$, it can be easily shown that at the maximum

$$\frac{1 - [X]}{[X]} = p/x \quad \dots (10)$$

The results are shown in Fig. 6.

It shows that $[HSal]_{org} : [Py]_{org}$ is as 1 : 1, in agreement with results given above.

On the basis of the results summarised above in (a) and (c) alone, the extracted species could have been represented as $Ni(Sal)_2(Py)(H_2O)$. This, however, is not in agreement with the result (b). The unit power dependence of $\log D$ on $\log [HSal]_{org}$ may be due to a reason similar to that in the extraction of metal ions by alkyl hydrogen

phosphate⁸ and DNNSA⁹. Results shown in Fig. 6 also indicate that the ratio $[\text{Py}]_{\text{org}} : [\text{HSal}]_{\text{org}}$ is unity.

FIG. 6

At high values of $[\text{Py}]_{\text{org}}$ the slope of the $\log D - \log [\text{Py}]_{\text{org}}$ plot tends to 1.5 indicating that the species $\text{Ni}(\text{Sal})_2(\text{Py})_2$ also is becoming equally important in the extraction process. It was not possible to obtain a two-power dependence within the range of concentration of pyridine studied and it did not seem justified to use very large concentration to test the partial differentials.

Steric effects: If one writes the mechanism of the enhanced extraction as

one can expect considerable steric hindrance if the position adjacent to the nitrogen in pyridine is substituted by a bulky group or radical. To test this the following three derivatives of pyridine, viz., α -picoline, β -picoline and α -bromopyridine, were used instead of pyridine. The results shown in table I show that there is no synergic enhancement for α -derivative whereas the β -derivative gives rise to synergic effects.

TABLE I

Extraction in presence of Pyridine derivatives

Derivatives	%Extraction
1. α -Bromopyridine (0.1M)	Negligible
2. α -Picoline "	"
3. β -Picoline "	72%

8. D. F. Peppard et al., *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **7**, 276.

9. J. M. White, P. Tang and N. C. Li, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1960, **14**, 255.

Preparation of the anhydrous chelate Ni(Sal)₂: To find out the optimum conditions at which the anhydrous complex Ni(Sal)₂ is obtained, thermogravimetric studies were carried out on the dihydrate. The results are shown in Fig. 7.

FIG. 7

The loss of weight between 100-300° corresponds to the loss of two water molecules, thus giving the anhydrous complex. Beyond this temperature, the complex starts to decompose. Based on these results the anhydrous product was prepared by heating the dihydrate in a current of dry nitrogen at $200 \pm 10^\circ$ for 4-5 hr. A bright yellow product was obtained which analysed as follows: Exp. 19.12%Ni; Cal. 19.5% Ni for Ni(C₇H₅O₂)₂. The slightly lower value may be due to the absorption of water during transfer, weighing, etc. The complex dissolves in benzene to give yellow solutions, as distinct from the greenish solutions of the pyridine adduct, though the dissolution takes place only very slowly. The slowness may be due to the sintering which would have occurred during the dehydration. However, the dissolution of the anhydrous complex is quite fast in presence of added pyridine to give again a greenish solution, possibly because of formation of the pure pyridine adduct.

The authors gratefully acknowledge Dr. J. Shankar, Head, Chemistry Division for his keen interest and encouragement. They also thank Dr. T. Kesava Das for helpful discussions.